

IMMUNOHISTOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE LUNGS CAUSED BY TITANIUM DIOXIDE AND ALUMINUM OXIDE.

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Annotation. Food additives have become widely used for a number of reasons: to extend the shelf life of food products that must be transported over long distances; to meet the changing tastes and preferences of consumers, the desire for economy and convenience, which has led to the introduction of additives such as flavors and colors; and because of the improvement of food production technologies.

Keywords: food additive, food safety, nanomaterial, oral exposure, titanium dioxide, toxicity.

Aim of the study. To study the morphology of the lungs of outbred white rats by the influence of food coloring and to compare the results after phytocorrection.

Introduction. The term "food additives" sounds alarming to many, although the use of some of them, such as salt, acetic acid and spices, dates back thousands of years. But over time, natural additives have given way to synthetic ones. To facilitate the identification of food additives with their complex and verbose scientific terms, a standardized labeling system has been introduced, where each substance is identified by the letter "E" followed by a numeric code. The letter "E" here is an indicator of European origin, and the following numbers classify the additive into the appropriate category, detailing its type and function .

According to their functionality, food additives are divided into the following categories:

- Dyes from E100 to E182 are involved in changing the color of products;
- Preservatives from E200 to E299 are used to extend the shelf life of food;
- Antioxidants, covering the E300-E399 series, prevent oxidation; Stabilizers and thickeners included in the range E400-E499 are responsible for maintaining the texture of products;
- Emulsifiers in the E500-E599 series create a uniform texture and prevent caking;
- Flavor and aroma enhancers are under the codes E600-E699;
- The range from E700 to E899 is left free for future use;

- Options from E900 to E999 include antifoaming agents and flame retardants .

Materials and methods. Serial sections with a thickness of 3 μm were dewaxed, dehydrated, unmasked and stained with antigens using a specialized automated system Ventana Benchmark XT, Roche, Switzerland. The study was carried out with the CD68 antibody.

The CD68 marker was evaluated according to the criterion of the presence or absence of cytoplasmic staining in alveolar and interstitial macrophages, and was assessed by a semi-quantitative method based on the severity of staining and the number of granules in the cytoplasm according to the following scheme:

Results of the study. The lung system of macrophages consists of several subpopulations that are found in different anatomical regions of the lungs, including the respiratory tract, alveolar spaces, and resident lung tissue. Alveolar macrophages make up more than 90% of the lung macrophage population. CD68 (cluster of differentiation 68, macrosialin – CD68 (clone of KP1)) is one of the specific markers of macrophages. Alveolar and interstitial macrophages are the two main subgroups, named after their location. Alveolar macrophages are responsible for clearing inhaled foreign particles of various nature. The interaction of alveolar macrophages with the removed particles through certain receptors determines the severity of the inflammatory response: from minimal to active inflammation with damage to lung tissue. In our study, it was found that in the “experimental” groups with signs of fibrotic changes, there was intense proliferation of CD68. In this case, staining is observed not only of alveolar and interstitial macrophages, but also of histiocytes located in the formed peribronchial lymphoid groups. Alveolar macrophages are responsible for the clearance of inhaled foreign particles of various natures, and their interaction with the removed particles through certain receptors determines the severity of the inflammatory response, which can vary from minimal to active inflammation with damage to lung tissue. The significant number of interstitial and alveolar macrophages indicates a strong inflammatory response of the lung tissue to the combined effect of TiO_2 and Al_2O_3 nanoparticles.

Thus, the obtained results indicate that titanium dioxide and aluminum oxide nanoparticles have a significant potential to induce inflammatory changes in lung tissue. The combined effect of these nanoparticles leads to a more pronounced inflammatory response.

Conclusion. In our study, it was found that in the "experimental" groups with signs of fibrotic changes, intensive proliferation of CD68 was noted. At the same

time, staining of not only alveolar and interstitial macrophages, but also histiocytes located in the formed peribronchial lymphoid groups was observed.

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